

Fungal Laccase: A Review of Its Production, Optimisation Purification and Application

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ABSTRACT

Laccases are multicopper oxidases, produced majorly by fungal species and are commonly used for dye degradation, bioremediation, waste detoxification and delignification. This study was performed to produce, optimize, purify and to analyse the degrading ability of the enzyme laccase; which is widely known for its high oxidative activity and low substrate specificity. This enzyme can be predominantly found in white-rot fungi and thus was isolated from a fungal species obtained from marine sample. In order to achieve maximal laccase activity, an optimized production medium containing Glucose [10g L⁻¹], MgSO₄·7H₂O [0.1g L⁻¹] and Yeast extract [5g L⁻¹] was used. Laccase formation was also stimulated by optimizing the value of CuSO₄[1.0 mM]. Further increase in concentration of CuSO₄ proved to be toxic to the organism. The enzyme assay was done in duplicates by using Guaiacol as the substrate in order to determine the enzyme activity. The purified extracellular laccase obtained after Ammonium Sulphate precipitation and DEAE- Cellulose chromatography was subjected to SDS- PAGE and had an apparent molecular mass of 66 kDa. The ability of Laccase to degrade chemical compounds using just molecular Oxygen was assessed through the degradation of Bisphenol-A, an Endocrine Disrupting Chemical.

Keywords: Laccase, white-rot fungi, optimisation, enzyme assay, Bisphenol-A.

INTRODUCTION

Enzymes are biological substances, i.e., biocatalysts that are used to speed up the biochemical reactions in living organisms and can be obtained from various sources like plants, animals, and microorganisms etc. They have a wide range of industrial applications [1]. One such enzyme is Laccase. Laccases (Benzenediol: oxygen oxidoreductases, E.C 1.10.3.2) are glycosylated polyphenol oxidases: 30% carbohydrate with a molecular mass of 60-90 kDa. These are exclusively known for the catalysis of mono-electron oxidation of both organic and inorganic substrates like aromatic amines, phenols, methoxyphenols, accompanied by the reduction of molecular oxygen to water [1,2]. Laccases are multicopper oxidases i.e., the active site of the enzyme contains four copper ions whose coordinated interaction is responsible for its function. The four copper ions are classified into three categories: Type 1 (T1), Type 2 (T2) and Type 3 (T3), depending on which the enzymes are further classified into three types: Blue, Yellow and White [3].

Figure 1: Diagrammatical representation of reduction of molecular oxygen to water by laccase

Laccases have high nonspecific oxidation capacity and they also have the ability to use molecular oxygen as electron acceptor [Fig 1]. This accounts for the diverse applications of laccase in the field of biotechnology [4]. Laccases are extracellular enzymes which were first found in the exudates of *Rhus vernicifera* [5]. These enzymes can be obtained from plants, bacteria, fungi and insects. *Azospirillum*

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lipoferum, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Streptomyces lavendulae*, *S. cyaneus* and *Marinomonas mediterranea* are some of the bacterial sources that produce laccase. Laccases produced by plants is limited when compared to that of microbial sources. In plants, laccases have been identified in turnips, cabbages, trees, asparagus, pears, potatoes, beets and other vegetables. Higher plant species also contain laccases; however, their characterization is less convincing. Out of all these sources, microbial sources are highly preferred since they are more reliable, easy to handle and maintain [3,5,6]. The enzymes are found in Ascomycetes, Basidiomycetes and Deuteromycetes and abundantly in White-rot fungi, which are known for their ability to degrade lignin in woods using the extracellular enzymes – lignin peroxidase, manganese – dependent peroxidase and laccase [6]. In addition to lignin degradation, fungal laccases play an important role in sporulation, pigment production, fruiting body formation and plant pathogenesis [7]. The four copper atoms in the enzyme are responsible for its catalytic activity and they cleave the following bonds - C α -oxidation, C α -C β cleavage and aryl-alkyl cleavage. However, the mono electron oxidation of the substrate accompanied by the reduction of molecular oxygen is not completely straightforward. A series of non-enzymatic reactions like disproportionation, hydration also takes place during the enzyme catalytic reaction [8]. Laccases often use low molecular weight compounds with high redox potential to oxidise the lignin portion of non-phenolic substances. These are called as mediators and they act as an “electron shuttle”. [Figure 2]. This molecule then diffuses away from the enzymatic pocket and thereby oxidises the available substrate [9]

Figure 2: Laccase-mediator oxidation system

Laccase catalysis occurs in three steps [Figure 3]: Type (1) copper reduction by substrate (2) Electron transfer from type 1 Cu to the type 2 Cu and type 3 Cu trinuclear cluster Reduction of oxygen to water at the trinuclear cluster.

Figure 3: Catalytic cycle of Laccase

In fungal species, laccases are monomeric, dimeric and tetrameric glycoprotein with a lesser polysaccharide content. Mannoses are one of the major carbohydrates attached to laccases and their molecular weight is reported to be around 50-97 kDa and the glycosylation ranges between 10% and 25%. An appreciable degree of heterogeneity is seen in laccases isolated from Ascomycetes, with respect to molecular weight [10,11]. Several isoenzymes of laccases have been found. Almost eight different laccase isoenzymes is said to have been produced by the white – rot fungus *P.ostreatus*, out of which only six of them have been isolated and characterised. Most of the wood-rotting fungi are monomeric proteins in nature. However, they also exhibit homodimeric structure, containing two identical subunits with a molecular weight similar to that of monomeric laccases. Laccases can be grouped according to their preference for ortho-, para-, meta-substituted phenols. Various natural and synthetic substrates oxidised by laccases have been identified and these are used to determine the enzymatic activity of laccase. However, not all substrates can be directly oxidised by laccase due to two reasons; One because of their large sizes which inhibits their penetration into the active site and another because of their high redox potentials. Hence, they require a mediator system that will be directly oxidised by laccase, which in turn will oxidise the potential targets. Laccases have ortho- and para-diphenol activity and hence substrate range varies from one laccase to another [12]. Laccase can be produced from various organisms. However, the amount of laccase produced is relatively low. Thus, in order to stimulate the production of laccase, inducers are used. Inducers are either natural substrates or substrate analogs that will

enhance the production of enzyme [13]. Inducers like vera aryl alcohol, ferulic acid, aromatic and phenolic substances can be used. In addition, increased Copper concentration in the medium has shown a positive result. Copper tends to improve the level of gene transcription for laccase enzyme. Since, the promoter region of the gene that encodes for laccase contains various recognition sites which are specific for copper and because of its easy availability, Copper is often used to induce the production of laccase [14]. Laccases are known for their wide industrial applications [Figure 4] such as, delignification and pulp bleaching, bioremediation, prevention of wine decolourisation, oxidation of dye and their precursors, waste detoxification, plant fiber modification, ethanol production, biosensors for the estimation of phenol or other enzymes in fruit juices, biofuel cells, production and treatment of beverages, enzymatic conversion of chemical intermediates and production of chemicals from lignin [15]. On account of their importance in variety of applications, this dissertation aims to produce, optimise and purify the laccase enzyme.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Laccases are extracellular enzymes which are secreted out in the medium by several fungi during secondary metabolism. In this literature, laccase was produced by a fungi isolated from tannery waste. This dissertation aims to efficiently produce laccase by identifying the suitable medium and modifying its components. Tannery wastewater sample was collected in a sterile bag and brought to the lab for further study. 1 ml of the collected sample was added to 10 ml of sterile water. This mixture was then serially diluted up to 10^{-7} dilutions and 1.0 ml of each dilution was spread on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates containing 4 mM Guaiacol as laccase inducer and was incubated at 30°C for 3–4 days. The positive strain was then subjected to Lactophenol Cotton Blue test, in order to study the organism's morphological and colonial characteristics. Distinct fungal colonies were further subculture to obtain pure cultures, which were then maintained on Potato Dextrose Agar Slants at 4°C. The mycelium from the slants was transferred to 200 ml of the Potato Dextrose Broth containing flask. The flask containing medium was incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days.

2.3 EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MEDIA

The following laccase production media were optimized for effective production of laccase:

- 1.MEDIA A (Meat Extract Medium)
- 2.MEDIA B (Sucrose Medium)
- 3.MEDIA C (Glucose Medium)

Table 1: Composition of Laccase Production Media A (Meat extract medium)

MEDIUM A	QUALITY (200 ML)
Meat Extract	1%
Sucrose	0.5%
Magnesium Sulphate	0.1%
Potassium Phosphate	0.3%

Table 2: Composition of Laccase Production Medium B (Sucrose medium)

Medium B	Quality (200 ml)
Sucrose	3%
Sodium Nitrate	0.2%
Magnesium sulphate	0.5%
Potassium sulphate	0.1%
Potassium chloride	0.5%

Table 3: Composition of Laccase Production Medium C (Glucose medium)

MEDIUM C	QUALITY (200 ML)
Glucose	2 g
Yeast extract	1 g
Sodium chloride	0.04 g
Magnesium Sulphate heptahydrate	0.02 g

3 flasks containing 100ml of media A, media B and media C were inoculated with 1 ml of the pre-inoculum. These flasks were incubated in a rotary shaker at 300 C and 120 rpm for 3-4 days

2.4 ENZYME ASSAY

1 ml of the 24 hours old culture media were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 mins at 4° C. The supernatant was then assayed to determine the enzyme activity.

2.4.1 Reagent preparation

1. Acetate buffer

36 ml of Sodium Acetate (0.82g/50 ml H₂O) was added along with 14 ml of Acetic Acid (600µl/50 ml H₂O) and was made up to 500 ml using distilled water.

2. Guaiacol

12.5µl of Guaiacol in 50 ml of Acetate Buffer.

Procedure

To 200µl of the supernatant, 800µl of Guaiacol was added and incubated for 5 mins. This step was performed individually for each production medium. The absorbance of the samples was determined spectrophotometrically at 454 nm after zeroing with a blank. The enzyme activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Enzyme Activity} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance} \times \text{dilution factor} \times \text{total volume})}{(\text{extension Coeff.} \times \text{volume of enzyme} \times \text{incubation time})}$$

The enzymatic activities are expressed as international units (U), defined as the amount of enzyme required to produce 1µmole product/minute [16].

2.5 OPTIMIZATION OF MEDIUM FOR LACCASE PRODUCTION BY CLASSICAL METHOD

The production medium was amended using various concentrations of Copper, Salt, Carbon and Nitrogen sources.

2.5.1 Effect of Copper Sulphate on laccase production

To induce the production of laccase, various concentrations (1.0 mM, 1.5 mM and 2.0 mM) of CuSO₄ were applied individually to 3 flasks containing 100 ml production media C (Glucose media) along with 1 ml of the inoculum. The flasks were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.5.2 Effect of carbon sources on laccase production

Monosaccharides like Glucose, Fructose, Lactose and Galactose were supplemented at 1% concentration to 3 separate flasks containing 1 mM CuSO₄ in 100 ml production medium C (Glucose medium) [17]. The flasks were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.5.3 Optimisation of Glucose concentration

Different concentrations (0.5%, 1% and 2%) of Glucose were applied to 3 distinct flasks containing 1 mM CuSO₄ in 100 ml production medium C (Glucose medium). The flasks were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.5.4 Effect of nitrogen sources on laccase production

The production medium C (Glucose medium) containing 1 mM CuSO₄ and 1% Glucose was modified using different nitrogen sources like Yeast extract, Mycological Peptone and Soybean Meal individually at 0.5% concentration [18]. The flasks were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.5.5 Optimization of Yeast extract concentration

Different concentrations of Yeast extract (0.5%, 1% and 2%) were added to 3 individual flasks containing 1 mM CuSO₄ and 1% Glucose in 100 ml production medium C (Glucose medium). The flasks were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.5.6 Optimization of Salt (Magnesium sulfate heptahydrate) concentration

The following concentrations of Magnesium Sulfate heptahydrate: 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.02% were examined to study its effect on laccase activity. Three separate flasks of production medium C (Glucose medium) containing 1 mM CuSO₄, 1% Glucose and 0.5% Yeast extract were incubated at 30° C in a rotary shaker at 120 rpm for 3–4 days. The enzyme activity was determined every 24 hours as described earlier. Enzyme assay was carried out in duplicate.

2.6 PROTEIN ISOLATION AND LACCASE PURIFICATION

The culture supernatant was initially filtered through Whatman filter paper to remove mycelia debris. The filtrate was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4° C and collected.

2.6.1 Ammonium Sulfate precipitation

The filtered broth obtained from the final optimized production was subjected to ammonium sulphate precipitation. 20% saturation of (NH₄)₂ SO₄ was added and equilibrated for 16 h at 4° C with constant stirring and the resultant precipitate was collected by centrifuging at 10,000 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The same solution was brought to 40, 60 and 80% saturation with ammonium sulphate and the precipitate was collected by the same procedure. The precipitates from different fractions were dissolved in 0.1 mM Acetate buffer, pH 5.0 and the fractions were subsequently analysed for activity. Although enzyme activity was found in all saturation maximum activity was observed in 60 percent fraction.

2.6.2 Dialysis

Buffer exchange was performed to the obtained precipitate using 10 mM sodium acetate buffer and constantly changing it every 6 hours in a dialysis membrane of 12 kDa (cut-off).

2.6.3 DEAE-Cellulose chromatography

The desalted enzyme solution was applied to pre-packed DEAE Cellulose column at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Bound proteins were eluted using Tris HCl buffer (pH 8.0) with a linear gradient of 1 M NaCl. Fractions were collected in 2 ml fraction collecting tube and their enzyme activities were determined. The

tubes showing activity were pooled together. These laccase rich fractions were cooled, concentrated and dialysed against Sodium Acetate buffer and stored until further use.

2.6.4 SDS-PAGE

Sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was performed in order to determine the purity of the enzyme. 20 µl of the laccase rich fractions, 10% resolving gel and a 4% stacking gel were used based on the method of Laemmli [19]. The protein bands were visualized by staining with Coomassie Brilliant Blue and were compared to standard molecular weight markers.

2.7 BISPHENOL-A DEGRADATION

Bisphenol-A (0.01%) was incubated with 0.64 U/ml of purified enzyme in 100 mM Sodium Acetate buffer at 30° C in dark. The amount of Bisphenol A was quantified at intervals by Electrospray Ionisation Mass Spectrometry.

3. RESULTS

3.1 ISOLATION AND SCREENING OF LACCASE PRODUCING ENZYME

The morphological and colonial identification of the positive fungal isolates was carried out by subjecting them to the Lactophenol Cotton Blue technique, followed by characterization by observing under the Scanning Electron Microscope.

Figure 4: Lactophenol Cotton Blue-Stained Fungi

Figure 5: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of Laccase producing fungi

3.2 EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MEDIA COMPOSITION ON LACCASE PRODUCTION

The purpose of this step was to identify the suitable medium for effective laccase production. The culture was inoculated into three different flasks containing Medium A (Meat extract medium), Medium B (Sucrose medium), and Medium C (Glucose medium). The organisms were grown at 30° C with continuous agitation (120 rpm) for 3–4 days, and laccase activity was measured at 24 h intervals. Under the specified conditions, maximum laccase activity was found on the 4th day in Medium C.

3.3 MEDIA OPTIMIZATION

3.3.1 EFFECT OF COPPER SULFATE ON LACCASE PRODUCTION

Laccases are multicopper oxidases therefore, copper as micronutrients key role as metal activators. For optimising copper concentration for higher laccase production, copper as CuSO₄ (1.0 mM, 1.5 mM, 2.0 mM) was added to three separate flasks containing 100 ml production medium c along with the other components.

3.3.2 EFFECT OF CARBON SOURCES ON LACCASE PRODUCTION

Monosaccharides like Glucose, Fructose, Lactose and Galactose were tested at 1% concentration. Glucose (50 U) had a positive effect on laccase production compared to other carbon sources [20,21].

3.3.3 OPTIMISATION OF GLUCOSE CONCENTRATION

Varying concentrations (0.5%, 1% and 2%) of Glucose were tested. Increased laccase activity (49.2 U) was observed in the flask containing 1% glucose on the 4th day.

3.3.4 EFFECT OF NITROGEN SOURCES ON LACCASE PRODUCTION

Nitrogen sources tested were Yeast extract, Mycological peptone and Soybean Meal at 0.5% concentration. Optimum enzyme production (49 U) was achieved when Yeast extract was used.

3.3.5 OPTIMIZATION OF YEAST EXTRACT CONCENTRATION

Yeast extract concentrations of 0.5%, 1% and 2% were tested. The highest level of enzyme formation (50.5 U) was obtained with 0.5% Yeast extract on the 4th day.

3.3.6 OPTIMIZATION OF SALT (MAGNESIUM SULFATE HEPTAHYDRATE) CONCENTRATION

Salt concentrations of 0.005%, 0.01% and 0.02% were examined. Enzyme activity was significantly higher on the 4th day in the flask containing 0.01% Magnesium Sulphate heptahydrate.

3.4 PROTEIN ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION

The purification began with ammonium sulphate salting-out at 60% saturation (resulting in 2.77-fold purification). This fraction was then subjected to DEAE-Cellulose chromatography.

Figure 6: Enzyme purification using DEAE-Cellulose column

The purified laccase showed a single band on SDS-PAGE with a molecular mass of 66 kDa.

Figure 7: SDS-PAGE of purified laccase after staining with Coomassie brilliant Blue; lane-1: standard marker protein, lane-2: DEAE purified enzyme

3.5 BISPHENOL-A DEGRADATION

Bisphenol-A was degraded by the purified laccase. ESI-MS analysis was conducted to identify the reaction product. ESI-MS analysis of Bisphenol-A control sample (Shows the control peak at $m/z, 277.15$). ESI-MS analysis of Bisphenol-A degradation by purified laccase (Shows peaks at $m/z, 453.22$ and 679.25) The peaks at $m/z, 453.22$ and 679.25 suggest that the enzyme has dimerized and trimerized Bisphenol-A into a less toxic form.

Figure 8: Enzyme Activity

Figure 9: Enzyme Activity assay

4. DISCUSSION

Laccase production by fungi is significantly affected by culture conditions. This enzyme is typically produced in low concentrations by fungi, but higher concentrations can be achieved by adding various supplements to the growth media. Laccase synthesis in this study was performed using three production media, all containing suitable carbon, nitrogen, copper, and salt concentrations. Based on the enzyme assay results, production medium-C was selected as the ideal medium for laccase synthesis [22].

Copper Optimization: Optimizing copper concentration is crucial because copper induces laccase activity. As laccases are multicopper oxidases, copper acts as a micronutrient and a key metal activator, regulating gene expression and positively affecting the enzyme's activity and stability. The optimal concentration for laccase synthesis was found to be 1 mM CuSO_4 .

Concentrations higher than this are normally toxic to the fungi and inhibit production. Carbon Source Optimization: Carbon sources are important for the production of ligninolytic enzymes like laccase. Laccase production is highly dependent on glucose concentration [22]. The enzyme assay showed that 1% concentration of glucose in the production medium resulted in the maximum enzyme activity.

Nitrogen Source Optimization: The nature and concentration of nitrogen sources are powerful nutritional factors that regulate laccase enzyme production, as nitrogen is essential for amino acid and protein synthesis. While nitrogen-sufficient media can enhance ligninolytic enzyme production in some cases, nitrogen depletion triggers laccase production in other fungal species. The optimal concentration for laccase production in this study was 0.5% of yeast extract. The purification of the enzyme is essential for its various applications. The initial step was ammonium sulphate precipitation at 60% saturation to precipitate the enzyme. Dialysis was performed to remove the salts from the enzyme. DEAE-Cellulose chromatography further ensured the purity of the enzyme based on the protein's charge. SDS-PAGE determined the final molecular weight of the purified enzyme to be 66 kDa. Finally, this purified extracellular laccase was used for the degradation of Bisphenol-A. The enzyme successfully degraded Bisphenol-A into dimers and trimers, making it less toxic than its original form.

5. SUMMARY

The present study focused on the production of the enzyme Laccase from a fungal species, its optimization, purification, and application in degrading the endocrine-disrupting chemical, Bisphenol-A. Laccase producing fungi were isolated from a tannery wastewater sample and screened using Guaiacol as an indicator. The organism was identified morphologically and screened using the Lactophenol Cotton Blue technique and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The organism was inoculated into three different media (Medium A, B, and C). Medium C was identified as the most suitable for Laccase production. The optimal concentration of the inducer CuSO_4 was determined to be 1.0 mM. Glucose was found to be the most effective carbon source at 1%

concentration. Yeast extract was the optimal nitrogen source at 0.5% concentration. The optimal salt concentration for maximum Laccase activity was 0.01% $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The Laccase was purified by Ammonium Sulfate precipitation (60% saturation) and DEAE-Cellulose chromatography. The final purity was confirmed by SDS-PAGE, which determined the apparent molecular weight of the enzyme to be 66 kDa. The purified extracellular Laccase was successfully used to degrade the Endocrine Disrupting Chemical Bisphenol-A. ESI-MS analysis confirmed the degradation, suggesting the enzyme catalysed the formation of Bisphenol-A dimers and trimers, rendering the chemical less toxic. This study demonstrates that the isolated fungal species is a potential source for Laccase production and its enzyme can be utilized for the bioremediation of environmental pollutants such as Bisphenol-A.

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